

Operation of TVET Institutions in Developing Countries in the Post-COVID Era: Future Directions

Tasnia Fatin, Prof. Dr. Sazali Abd Wahab

PhD candidate, Putra Business School (PBS), Universiti Putra Malaysia (UPM),
Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia
tasniafatin6@gmail.com

Putra Business School (PBS), Universiti Putra Malaysia (UPM),
Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7268144

ABSTRACT

The Covid-19 pandemic was the most impactful event of our lives and caused the most upheaval in key areas. Due to the pandemic, the education sector took an unanticipated turn. The pandemic has influenced billions of learners worldwide, the learning process, learning institutions, linked groups, learner and teacher lifestyles, the learning environment, and learning-related enterprises. The rising usage of technology has changed the learning process. Covid has restricted learning chances, worsening social inequities. Any impairment to learning threatens long-term economic and human growth. The vocational and technical education and training (TVET) provides work-based learning primarily through offering face-to-face schooling. TVET has few remote-learning options. Most TVET institutes closed because of the pandemic. Since covid-19 was a problem that the whole globe was dealing with, solving it would require international cooperation. According to World Bank reports, most pupils worldwide suffered school closures during the pandemic's peak in late March 2020. During this time, educational institutions struggled to maintain face-to-face learning sessions while fighting the disease. These institutions eventually shifted to face-to-face remote learning. Even in gloomy times, great chances arose. All organizations went through coping, intermediate, and recovery, according to the 2020 World Bank blog. TVET students helped with the covid-19 reaction during the coping period. When organizations and schools reopened, 'new normal' safety precautions were scrupulously followed. TVET could train professionals at this point. In the recovery period, we hope for TVET reform based on prior experience. Investments are promising. Tackling the covid-19 epidemic has led to novel learning methodologies as an alternative to face-to-face learning. This article focuses on the new potential for TVET organizations following the covid-19 pandemic and gives insights into possible reformation strategies for the TVET sector to maintain sustained performance.

Keywords: Covid-19, TVET, Face-to-face schooling, World Bank.

How to Cite: First Author, Second Author, (Year). Type the Research Title. *LC International Journal of STEM* Volume. 2 No. (3), XX– XX. DOI:

INTRODUCTION

With the crisis of the COVID-19 pandemic, there is a dire need for adequate training and education to face this crisis properly. This has affected over 1.2 billion students in the world, especially with the lockdown and closures of educational organizations which also include Technical and Vocational Education & Training (TVET). To cope with the challenges remote learning was adopted using the internet. Since covid requires students to focus on developing work readiness and gaining practical skills, the remote learning process has turned out to be a poor substitute for practical tasks. To cope with the challenges students could participate in practical activities where business was allowed to open. Clinical training could be a potential part and it would even prove to be an effective engagement for the TVET students (HOFTIJZER et al., 2021).

According to the study of the International Labor Organization - Covid-19 Response plan for Bangladesh TVET sector (2021), the TVET system in Bangladesh has had to face difficulties in two major areas, TVET administration as well as TVET delivery. At the administration level it was regarding the disruption of - programmatic activities, field-level activities, achieving long-term progressive activity, effective monitoring, decision making, coordination with growth partners, etc. also there was the slow development of admin activity. TVET delivery was also affected by learning loss, practical learning loss, interrupted access, unwillingness to participate in the alternative approach to learning, etc.

According to another study conducted by International Labor Organization - Skills development in the time of COVID-19 (2021), by the middle of the second quarter of the year 2020, between April and May, roughly 14 percent of the total working hours had been lost across the globe, which is equivalent to the loss of 480 million full-time jobs. The labor market, in particular, saw rapid disturbance which represented a significant setback in terms of reaching the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 8 - 'Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all, as well as the target, which was required to be achieved by 2030 - 'full and productive employment and decent work for all. With the pandemic going on, the impact on work modality has also been noteworthy. One-third of the working population around the world belonged to countries required to close the workplace apart from emergency workers. Other 42 percent of them belonged where partial closure of workplace was. Nonetheless, to keep the business running, a workforce was needed where the requirements were. They needed to adapt to a regular approach to work. 'Teleworking', popularly known as 'WFH (Work from Home)' was the most effective method adopted worldwide while being proven beneficial in times of lockdown for both employer and employees in terms of cost-effectiveness and time-saving.

The education sector also got affected like the work sector in times of lockdown. Notably, it became one of the most disrupted sectors (ILO, 2021) and it halted the progress of SDG 4, 'Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. According to the report of World Bank (2020), approximately 1.6 billion students around the world were affected by the closure of educational institutions by the end of March 2020, when the pandemic was at its peak.

For TVET organizations, the covid-19 pandemic was a big challenge. Since the nature of this education requires face-to-face methods of teaching because of practical and work-based teaching. The scale of the TVET education disruption was very shocking (ILO, 2021).

Many educators and trainers lacked the required preparation necessary to adapt to different pedagogical modalities, maintain students' engagement and motivation through distance learning, and effectively manage classes while they were located remotely (ILO, 2021). Reorienting their training tactics in a short amount of time caused a tremendous lot of stress, pressure, and anxiety which undermined the working circumstances of the teaching staff. In other situations, instructors were not fully equipped with the essential equipment and internet connection. It was difficult for some instructors to juggle their professional and personal commitments, such as providing care for their children, and in other nations and locations, prolonged in-person training prompted worries over the teachers' safety and health (ILO, 2021).

The survey conducted by ILO in 2020 illustrates TVET systems' lack of resilience in a crisis of the magnitude and type of COVID-19 and whether that lack of readiness might compound the issues already present in such systems. The crisis has highlighted the absence of suitable technological infrastructure, digital literacy, and pedagogical materials as well as the detrimental repercussions that this may have in the short and long term, particularly for the most vulnerable demographic groups.

Despite all that, according to HOFTIJZER et al., (2021), 2020 has been recognized as a time for intense creativity. According to the blog of the World Bank in 2021, because of the pandemic, the TVET sector was exposed to weakness in its system. There were measures taken on to prevent the weaknesses with innovative experiments. The scale of those experiments indicates that major change is possible in this sector. With the reopening of educational institutions, there is an immediate need to develop skills along with the mechanisms tailored for both changing needs of the labor market and the individual need of the student.

It could be a great window of opportunity for stakeholders, sensing the dire need and potential for structural reformation of TVET for the sake of greater skill development and job. According to Hoftizer et al., (2021) in their world bank blog, there has been mention of taking innovative approaches to TVET learning and utilizing the remote learning opportunities by partnering up

How is training being provided in this period of the COVID-19 pandemic?

with the service providers i.e., telecommunication operators, technology providers, government, and partners.

Figure 1: TVET training providing method Source: ILO-UNESCO-World Bank online survey, 2020

Madu & Edokpolor (2021) in their article, discussed the possible issues and challenges that are faced by the TVET sector concerning teaching and learning during the time of the pandemic. According to them, the students and teachers were not prepared for the sudden transition to online education. Lacking the right qualifications and infrastructure to handle online teaching and learning methodologies, TVET professors and students were unlikely to be ready for the unanticipated shift to online education.

METHODOLOGY

There have been a lot of discussions regarding the effect of the covid-19 pandemic on the TVET sector and the problems and challenges it faced while keeping up. The possible ways to reform the TVET sector have been identified in light of published reports by ILO, World Bank, and the British Council and peer-reviewed published journal articles that would direct future operations. In total, eight articles have been reviewed in this review paper.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Disruptions on TVET

In the report published by ILO on 'Skills development in the time of COVID-19: Taking stock of the initial responses in technical and vocational education and training, it is mentioned that from the beginning of the crisis, in the learning and teaching area, innovative approaches have emerged.

Figure 2: TVET scenario on COVID-19 Source: ILO.org, 2022

A survey was conducted in 126 countries between the 5th of April and to 15th of May 2020 with the collaboration of UNESCO and the World Bank by ILO which covered policymakers, TVET providers, and social partners.

TVET delivers training and education at varying levels of skill relevant to a wide range of job opportunities, including education and training for plumbers, sales employees, electricians, accountants, programmers, etc. TVET also provides education and training for bank tellers. Because of their hands-on practical nature, the training programs have presented their participants with a unique set of obstacles.

At the onset of the epidemic, few nations and training institutions had enough equipment, connection, remote education software and systems, and pedagogical supplies. Furthermore, most students and teachers originally missed the digital abilities required to respond and then use the TVET facilities.

The transition to teaching via remote means has been an exercise in 'learning by doing.' Examples from the paper that were highlighted revealed the development of flexible monitoring and assessment alternatives. These options ranged from high-tech to low-tech or just no-tech solutions. These include using offline platforms such as national television networks to publicize practical knowledge inside a lot of nations such as Madagascar, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Pakistan. Additionally, the advancement of self-paced educational guides and

simulated skills assessments are also included in this category. Students in several nations document their work on real-world projects at home by filming and photographing their efforts and then uploading the content to online sites.

There has also been the formation of new (PPP) public-private partnerships, one example of which is the distribution of digital equipment to underprivileged students and instructors. New policy measures have also been implemented in certain nations to make certain that TVET programs are prepared for potential upcoming shocks. Over two-thirds of TVET operators said they delivered training exclusively via remote techniques during the pandemic, but only a small percentage of those in lower-income nations were able to make the switch. The paper cautions that unless the digital gap is bridged, concerns with providing internet learning modalities as well as infrastructure would leave disadvantaged students behind.

The Effects of COVID-19 on the TVET Industry

The continuity of TVET was severely hampered as a result of the unexpected closing of the vast majority of TVET centers, which was the consequence of national lockdowns being declared in several nations. Even though alternatives for distance learning were investigated and used to some extent, they were not capable of replacing the value of face-to-face courses. This is especially true when considering the exceptional emphasis that TVET places on learning through work-based experiences and the development of practical skills. It is anticipated that the effects of the crisis will continue after the lockdown period has ended. This is because households and TVET centers may find themselves in financially precarious positions compared to their previous states and unable to guarantee the consistency of training activities (ILO, 2021).

- Closure of TVET centers

According to the survey conducted in the report by ILO, almost 90 percent of respondents stated that there was a full-on closure in their countries on TVET centers due to the government taking measures on stopping the spread of the virus. Respondents who reported a total shutdown were located in nations that, in general, had the strictest government responses. Respondents who reported a partial lockdown, either for only some activities or regions, followed those who reported a complete closure. Those respondents who lived in nations with the least stringent average standards were the ones who reported no closures.

- Lacking proper skills

According to Madu & Edokpolor (2021), due to a lack of required skills and infrastructure, it was unlikely for TVET students and professors to be equipped for the unanticipated shift to online learning. This is because online learning and teaching techniques cannot be accommodated by existing teaching and learning methods. In Nigeria, the adoption of the learning and teaching process in TVET programs during the coronavirus period appears to be hampered by issues relating to energy supply, internet access, limited data transfer capacity, as well as a lack of available bandwidth to cope with increased data traffic.

Figure 3: Skill Shortage Source: ILO-UNESCO-World bank online survey, 2020

- Infrastructural resource quality

When it comes to large-scale deployment of OLMPs and instructional materials to support virtual instruction, TVET programs often fall short, as the COVID-19 issue has demonstrated (International Labor Organization, 2020; United Nations, 2020). Due to their lack of comprehensive integration into traditional programs, these OLMPs may not have proper quality or capacity monitoring, which might hamper a seamless experience of an online form of learning. For example, a lack of proper OLMPs and other technical capabilities might impair the effectiveness of students' and lecturers' training, which could lead to inefficient or less efficient learning experiences.

- Revenue Circulation

The COVID-19 pandemic outbreak along with the impact of constant lockdown and physical isolation measures have created issues for TVET providers' financial resource sustainability and cash flow. This is due to a rapid loss of money from sources such as school fees and other revenue resources generated by TVET programs. For example, TVET operators in Nigeria have had their financial sustainability eroded as a result of school dropouts and parents' failure to afford tuition. Students are likely to drop out of TVET programs as a result of this. This unfortunate condition will undoubtedly have an impact on TVET providers' capacity to contribute time and money to the creation of online learning infrastructure, as well as, in certain circumstances, pay lecturers' salaries (ILO, 2021).

Due to TVET's focus on face-to-face instruction and limited remote capabilities, several training centers have closed. Over 90% of respondents from 63 countries mentioned TVET school closures. Throughout South-East Asia and the Pacific, periodic shutdowns are common. Work-based education and apprentice programs have been hit hardest by the epidemic, and younger people are vulnerable in a shrinking labor market.

Flexible learning is not common in the skills industry. Before the pandemic, ILO-UNESCO-World Bank estimated that 16% of organizations had adopted remote learning. Remote learning is the most difficult to recreate for skills training that relies on industry-standard gear. Few teachers at TVET institutes are equipped to produce remote learning resources, and learners lack digital abilities and/or technology. The pandemic has shown this model's limits. COVID-19 impact has encouraged the sector's transformation while being realistic about short-term and low-tech options (ILO, 2021).

Main Obstacles in Continuing TVET training

This crisis appears to have exacerbated TVET's challenges and limits. In most nations, respondents for the World Bank and ILO (2020) survey recognized a move toward remote training to assure training continuity, although the survey results emphasized TVET systems' preparation for this problem. TVET managers, instructors, and learners were unprepared for the move to remote learning due to a lack of skills and infrastructure. The rapid move to distant learning and discrepancies in access to online training modules might worsen quality training inequalities among learners. Based on the survey conducted by ILO (2021) replies, several of these difficulties are listed below.

- Insufficient electricity, internet, connection, and gadgets

Learners in many nations lacked internet access. TVET instructors and other participants from low-income countries including Bangladesh, Afghanistan, the Central African Republic, Chad as well as the Democratic Republic of the Congo faced problems with internet access. Colombia, Albania and Costa Rica participants lacked internet and technology as well. Online classes were provided in the Philippines during the COVID-19 pandemic, but due to infrastructural issues (availability of gadgets and electronic devices), problems were not solved. Access to technical equipment is a problem worldwide. Even in high-income nations like Spain, TVET organizations note that many learners lack the equipment needed to perform training and educational activities (Wi-Fi, tablet, computer, etc.) that support online learning.

- Digital gap between urban regions and rural regions.

The gap in technological advancement between rural and urban regions is a problem in many nations. In Côte d'Ivoire, Trinidad & Tobago and Sri Lanka where the government is providing distant training via digital platforms as well as television, TVET suppliers and other respondents revealed that trainees in remote locations have been unable to gain from these measures due to a lack of interconnection or gadgets like computer systems and TVs. Participants from Finland, Spain, France, and the UK noted variations between rural and urban pupils' internet connectivity and digital equipment. TVET services in Ecuador claimed that internet availability and quality were poorer in rural regions than in cities. In certain rural regions of Malaysia, an electric generator supplies power for a few hours every day, according to a national training body. The digital gap between the rural region and urban regions likely worsened inequality in many nations.

- Scarcity of efficient and user-friendly distant learning solutions

The functioning of the educational platforms and technologies that are used in the delivery of various programs has a significant impact on the overall quality of remote learning. The COVID-19 emergency has brought to light the fact that impactful online educational platforms and the reliability of pedagogical funds to facilitate remote instruction are completely lacking throughout vocational education or training systems. This is especially the case when these platforms and resources are required to be mobilized on a global scale. This may be attributable to the fact that these systems are not completely integrated with regular programming; consequently, their quality and capacity are not adequately monitored which impedes a smooth transition to a primarily remote mode of learning. In addition, this may be attributable to the fact that their monitoring is inadequate.

Students and instructors may have a less successful learning experience without adequate platforms and resources. A Costa Rican TVET provider said TVET trainees resisted the rapid shift in teaching techniques.

Many TVET trainers were unfamiliar with distance learning. TVET providers and an Australian training administrative representative said instructors struggled to utilize Zoom & Skype to connect with students. Armenian TVET providers found it difficult to integrate new technology and shift learning online. A UK training authority official highlighted a cultural resistance to adopting online TVET courses. Bangladesh and Brunei Darussalam also have TVET providers with similar complaints.

- Inadequately skilled staff to support distant learning with high-quality pedagogical resources

As a result of a low range of online skills, TVET companies in many nations, including Canada, Morocco, the Republic of Korea, and India have reported that TVET teachers and students are not open to accepting distance-learning methods. This lack of preparedness is a result of the low range of online skills. The financial crisis has shed light on the underinvestment in those areas of teacher development that include developing the capability to run online learning systems efficiently and to produce pedagogical resources that can be used in completely remote learning and training.

- Financial Constraints

The outbreak of health emergency and the subsequent lockdown caused problems with cash flow and the providers' capacity to remain financially viable, particularly for the smaller TVET service providers. This might be linked to the unexpected loss of money from resources such as tuition costs and the income-earning operations of TVET centers. Both of these contributed significantly to the budget of the institution. The incapacity of parents to pay tuition and the loss of students have both contributed to a decline in the financial sustainability of training centers in Chad and the Democratic Republic of the Congo, according to the providers. The incapacity of parents to pay tuition is likely to result in young people withdrawing from technical and vocational education and training (TVET) programs. The subsequent impact on financial affairs has limited the capacity of TVET centers to invest time & expense in the infrastructure development for correspondence courses and in certain cases, to pay lecturers' salaries.

IMPLICATION OF THE STUDY

First and foremost, the importance of remote learning and the prerequisites for its high-quality provision are among the lessons learned from recent pandemic phases. Second, particular socio-emotional skills and behavior are essential for people to weather or rebound from crises. And third, readiness for future crises is also among the lessons learned. All sorts of respondents,

from government officials to members of training institutes, underlined these three areas in their responses, regardless of the country's degree of development.

Respondents said the pandemic accelerated attempts to increase remote learning alternatives and boosted competence in remote training. During the World Bank survey (2020), an official of an international group said that in Morocco, the government's Morocco Digital 2025 Strategy was expedited by the necessity to rely more on digital techniques for COVID-19.

A TVET operator in China noticed how the crisis boosted instructors' abilities to use technology and build online teaching materials (ILO, 2021).

There are suggestions from the survey response in this area-

- All TVET stakeholders must spend more on digital technology and skills to strengthen the system.
- Particular efforts are required to ensure the involvement and learning of students who are at a disadvantage through the use of remote learning.
- Because the dynamics of remote learning differ from those of face-to-face training, new teaching techniques are required to promote optimal student commitment and learning.
- The difficulties of imparting technical skills through remote learning is a unique challenge for TVET, demanding investment in novel learning approaches and increased flexibility.

In the second part, some respondents mentioned certain socio-emotional abilities, behaviors, and beliefs that came in handy during the crisis response. Participants of TVET organizations in Mexico emphasized the need for collaboration and solidarity among students, parents, and instructors. Members of TVET organizations in China and Ecuador, among others, stressed the need for adaptability and openness to change. A TVET institution in Armenia underlined the relevance and necessity of developing mutual respect, honesty, and fundamental principles to adapt to problems. Many respondents in Japan, China, Kyrgyzstan, Mexico, and Malaysia emphasized the significance of students' attitudes about learning in aiding their transition to distant, self-directed learning.

TVET providers and other respondents from Armenia, Ecuador, Jordan, Ghana, Kiribati, Malaysia, the Philippines, Mexico, and Sri Lanka were among those who stressed the significance of being well-prepared for any future crises. The vocational and technical education and training (TVET) operators in Uzbekistan and Mexico said that they were unprepared for crises, particularly of this scale. The representatives of employer groups from the Philippines and Ghana as well as those of TVET providers from Ecuador and Sri Lanka emphasized the significance of being well-prepared and having a backup strategy in place in the event of unforeseen emergencies in the future. A TVET provider representing Jordan noted that the risk response plan has to establish priorities and ought to be realistic in identifying what would be viable to achieve during moments of emergency. During times of crisis, in addition, representatives of training institutions in Kiribati and Malaysia implied that arrangements for a possible disaster included the advancement of an important role in the progress of faculty and administrators so that they can be prepared for and relate to changing teaching modalities. This was mentioned by representatives of trainers in both countries. Overall, there was a wide acceptance that unpreparedness for the COVID-19 emergency had made a contribution to the difficulties posed by TVET providers and that a useful lesson could be depicted from those insufficiencies to motivate incentive to invest in better-prepared anticipation of future crises.

HOLISTIC RECOMMENDATIONS

There are several possible recommended solutions according to the British Council report, ILO published reports, and world bank reports. Going further in this article, some possible solutions to the existing issues are explained-

In the report published by the British Council on June 2021, regarding the ways of innovation and changes due to covid-19, the British Council has conducted research consisting of five countries and three TVET institutions from each, a total of 15 TVET institutions. According to the report, 92 percent of respondents' answer was their organization had gone through several changes in institutional policies. The seeking answer was if the change needed to be kept even after the pandemic and if needed which area should be focused on. The report suggested that structural changes be made focusing on the three areas-

- Management and leadership
- Learning, teaching & quality assurance
- Finance

There are also recommendations for policymakers and TVET practitioners & leaders-

- To adapt to shifting conditions in the labor market, policymakers at the national level responsible for education should consider the extent to which the Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) curriculum should be decentralized.
- The possibility of national digital training programs for employees working in TVET institutions ought to be taken into consideration by policymakers.
- In the post-Covid-19 skill recovery programs, policymakers ought to place a higher priority on the effect on rural areas, populations with a lower socioeconomic status, and women.
- If an institution does not already have one, it should design a digital learning plan and expand on the successful practices that were implemented during the pandemic.
- A business continuity strategy is necessary at every institution's leadership level for managing risk and emergency scenarios. This plan has to be evaluated consistently.
- To ensure efficient communication with their workforce, institutions must devise strategies for internal communication and follow them.
- If they do not already have one, institutions that provide TVET should design a learner engagement plan that explicitly takes into account the accessibility of education for students who live in rural or otherwise difficult-to-reach areas.
- If an employer engagement plan has not previously been developed by an institution, it ought to be developed immediately. There should be a distinct component within the plan that focuses on developing sectors of the economy in which educational institutions and businesses may collaborate to make up for the possibilities that were eliminated as a result of COVID-19.
- Examination of an organization's work-based program should be carried out to discover new avenues open to employer participation in terms of postings, projects, and evaluations.
- Organizations need to develop a digital route plan for their employees so that they may acquire the knowledge and new concepts necessary for their work at the appropriate rate.
- Organizations must make it a priority to incorporate the cultivation of digital skills into their Continuous Professional Development (CPD) policies.
- Procedures for helping students remotely should be incorporated into the student assistance and safety policies of educational institutions.

There was also a recommendation provided in the ILO report in 2021. The ideas that are presented below identify the three primary areas in which stakeholders in TVET might collaborate both during & after the COVID-19 epidemic. They provide an outline of the primary steps that may be taken to improve readiness for future crises, lessen the negative influence of such catastrophes by increasing opportunities for education and boost the usefulness of TVET throughout the stage of recovery following the crisis.

Improve crisis-response preparedness

- Invest in the creation of proper crisis-response strategies for the education system at all levels, from national to the provider. These should provide enough emphasis on TVET-specific characteristics such as practical skill procurement and work-based education as well as expenditures in the development of appropriate ability to carry out these plans. These strategies should be integrated as much as feasible with the business sector, both as suppliers of work-based education and as key participants in the broader skills development system.
- Develop and strengthen the skills of TVET instructors and learners as well as TVET institution management to adapt to continually changing conditions whether from the COVID-19 pandemic or any future crises. This involves capacity building for collaborative learning which combines face-to-face and distant training, online and physical instruction and high-tech options, low-tech options, and no-tech options based on regional and national circumstances and changing skills demands of sectors and organizations. Peer-to-peer learning can be promoted for instructors and students to learn from past obstacles, exchange successful teaching and learning approaches and provide mutual support.

Improve education and training access

- Enhance internet infrastructure and make connectivity cheaper. People, particularly in nations with low and intermediate incomes, have a tough time gaining internet access due to a variety of circumstances that make it very hard for them. A lack of digital awareness, the comparatively high price of gadgets and data, and digital legislative and operational impediments are some of the things that fall into this category. Authorities must investigate measures to lower the cost of telecoms, improve network performance, make services cheaper, increase digital competition, and help needy populations through the use of digital subsidies.
- Invest in building and maintaining convenient access to TVET distant learning tech remote learning platforms must be developed to prepare teaching methods for crisis and well beyond. Practical skills growth has suffered more since they're tougher to teach online. TVET providers, governments, and other stakeholders, along with the commercial sector should innovate to overcome future difficulties.
- National collaboration with commercial companies in the education technology sector. There have been several potential education technology efforts launched throughout the world as a result of start-ups or even social programs by non-government corporations. These initiatives have the potential to improve educational outcomes. TVET systems should make an effort to interact with specialists in this field so that they may benefit from the information that is already available and the work that is being done by business ventures in their nation. This will make it possible for the TVET industry to profit from the growth of digital learning and to make use of individualized resources for trainees, which will result in improved training programs.
- To guarantee that individuals experience broad access to learning possibilities throughout their working career, emphasize equity and inclusivity. While many

development partners focus on young folks, training for grownups of formal employment receives far less attention, although it is relevant in terms of lifelong learning. The emphasis should not just be on school-to-work migrations but also on work-to-work transformation and young folk's and adults' developing skills and re-skilling. Employees in non-standard or short-term jobs must also be addressed because they frequently lack adequate training opportunities. Furthermore, when implementing digital solutions, particular attention should be paid to the great basic limitations faced by population subgroups, such as limited access to online devices and networks in remote regions or through women, and a productive labor market new policies should be implemented to benefit such disadvantaged people.

Provide necessary skills and training to help rebuild better

- Promptly, adjust to the changing conditions in the economy, the labor market, and society in general and teach young people and adults to fulfill the present and future needs of individuals with certain skill sets.
- Successful emerging breakthroughs in new training programs, learning systems, and resources should be integrated into the TVET system. In responding to the evolving needs and capacity constraints during the pandemic, several practical training solutions were produced along with distant teaching and learning support techniques. Mainstreaming them in TVET will boost resilience and build systems' ability to deploy them swiftly in future crises. If all lessons are learned and successes are maintained, system-level repercussions will be secured.
- Validate and recognize all learning. The pandemic accelerated digital learning at TVET. This achievement should be used to validate, recognize, and utilize digital learning skills. With the rise of MOOCs and academic technologies, validation and acknowledgment of informal and non-formal learning must be improved. Micro certificates, digital badges, and world reference levels may aid. Partnering with the business sector to recognize skills would assist to ensure their maximum output. Skills recognition is key to social participation, especially for migratory workers.
- Rebuild and achieve full employment via re-skilling and up-skilling workers. This is especially crucial for self-employed and informal sector employees who lost jobs or faced unemployment due to the pandemic. Education and training can help employees and organizations transfer from hard-hit to booming areas. Investing in life-long learning platforms with financial as well as non-financial incentives improve learning, particularly in moments of emergency. Social protection and financial stability should be added to enable study and career transitions. Robust and complicated skills initiatives may be costly; thus, they should be included in fiscal recovery policies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It has been well-documented that TVET (Training and Vocational Education and Training) provides practical and work-based learning. As a result, corporations provide face-to-face learning experiences. In the case of TVET, the option of remote learning is extremely limited. Most TVET institutes were closed as a result of the pandemic. During this time, educational institutions struggled to maintain regular face-to-face learning sessions while also attempting to contain the disease's spread.

Combating the covid-19 epidemic has paved the opportunity for educational institutions to establish creative learning methodologies as an alternative to face-to-face learning. This review

paper focused on the new opportunities created for TVET organizations as a result of the covid-19 epidemic, as well as providing insights into the information that could lead to possible reformation policies for the TVET sector to ensure the long-term performance of TVET institutions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors are grateful to the editors of the journal. Special thanks go to Ms. Nusrat Hafiz, lecturer at BRAC University, for her support to produce and publish the review study in the journal.

REFERENCES

- Madu, M. C., & Edokpolor, J. E. (2021). Issues and Challenges Facing The Teaching and Learning of Tvet in The Covid-19 Pandemic Era. *Journal of Vocational Education Studies*, 4(2), 188-195.
- Chun, H. K., Comyn, P., & Moreno da Fonseca, P. (2021). Skills development in the time of COVID-19: taking stock of the initial responses in technical and vocational education and training. Geneva: International Labour Office.
- Association of Colleges (Great Britain)(AoC). (2021). How are vocational institutions innovating, evolving, and changing as a result of COVID-19?: a study of practice and perspectives in five countries.
- Australia. Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade. Human Development and Governance Division. Education Section. (2020). The skills sector and COVID-19: practical actions.
- HOFTIJZER, M., LEVIN, V., & WEBER, M. (2021). *COVID-19 highlights the urgency of TVET reforms*. World Bank Blogs. Retrieved 24 June 2022, from <https://blogs.worldbank.org/education/covid-19-highlights-urgency-tvet-reforms>.
- Skills development in the time of COVID-19: Taking stock of the initial responses in technical and vocational education and training. Ilo.org. (2022). Retrieved 27 June 2022, from https://www.ilo.org/skills/areas/skills-training-for-poverty-reduction/WCMS_766557/lang-en/index.htm.
- ILO-UNESCO-World Bank Webinar on TVET and skills development in the time of COVID-19. Ilo.org. (2022). Retrieved 27 June 2022, from https://www.ilo.org/skills/WCMS_767987/lang-en/index.htm.
- Skills development in the time of COVID-19: Taking stock of the initial responses in technical and vocational education and training. Ilo.org. (2022). Retrieved 5 September 2022, from https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_emp/---ifp_skills/documents/publication/wcms_767890.pdf.
- ILO-UNESCO-WBG Joint Survey on Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) and Skills Development during the time of COVID-19. Ilo.org. (2022). Retrieved 5 September 2022, from https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_emp/---emp_ent/documents/genericdocument/wcms_742817.pdf.